

A STUDY ON JOB SATISFACTION OF SPINNING MILL WORKER IN ARUPPUKOTTI TOWN

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Abstract:

Human resource is an important asset of any organization. In this era of competitive world, success of any organization depends on its human resource. If they are highly satisfied with the job they produce more which is profitable for the organization. The objective of our study is to measure the level of satisfaction of workers in spinning mill workers. If workers do not trust the organization or interviewer, however, responses may not be entirely honest. Businesses with low job satisfaction who fear being let go may find the workers reluctant to discuss the situation since they may fear it could negatively affect them in the future.

Key Words: Job Satisfaction & Spinning Mill Workers,

Introduction:

Human resource is an important asset of any organization. In this era of competitive world, success of any organization depends on its human resource. If they are highly satisfied with the job they produce more which is profitable for the organization. So in this competitive environment, the essential thing is to know the views of workers toward their job and to measure the level of satisfaction with various aspects of job satisfaction

The term 'job satisfaction' means individuals emotional reaction to job. It is a positive emotional state that occurs when a person's job seem to fulfill important job values provided. The objective of our study is to measure the level of satisfaction of workers in spinning mill workers. If workers do not trust the organization or interviewer, however, responses may not be entirely honest. Businesses with low job satisfaction who fear being let go may find the workers reluctant to discuss the situation since they may fear it could negatively affect them in the future.

Scope of the Study:

Quality of Work Life is the major significant factors for the employees in the organization. The study covers employees Private hospitals. A satisfied employee will be having a positive attitude towards his or her job and would go beyond the normal expectation in his other job.

Need for the Study:

The study may encourage the employees and management to bring changes in the perception necessary for effective and efficient performance.

Objective of the Study:

- ✓ To understand the measure of job satisfaction amongst spinning mill workers.
- ✓ To identify various components contributing towards the job satisfaction.

Review of Literature:

The author examined various components in the individual's factors like individual's lifestyle, satisfaction, career, and training and development, rewards and compensation. The researchers focused on Quality work life among factory workers will lead to better performance. The employees with high commitment and positive work attitude would create support for the workers quality of work life.

The author describes that Quality of work life is based on performance. Quality of Work Life has positive relations with performance and developing human capabilities in the work organization.

The researchers examined that quality of work life is defined by different factors such as work-life balance, social factors, economic factors, job factors.

The author examined that quality of work life is the degree to which members of a work organization are able to satisfy important personal needs through their experience in the organization.

Sampling Design:

A Sample of 50 respondents has been drawn from the various socio-economic strata, at different designation and having different educational qualification and belongs to different age-groups on the line of "Convenience Sampling" method. In this method, the sample units are chosen primarily on the basis of the convenience to the researcher.

Sample Size:

Subjects of the present study were selected from managerial and non-managerial staff of spinning mill industry. In this research our sample size is 50. Simple random sampling was used to collect the data.

Primary Data:

Under this study primary data was collected by using structured questionnaire. The primary data has been collected through the questionnaire by means of personal interview.

Secondary Data:

The secondary data are sourced from various telecommunication websites, magazines, Books and periodical survey etc.,

Statistical Tools Used for this Study:

The data has been mainly analyzed by using the following methods and test.

- ✓ Percentage analysis
- ✓ Chi-square test

Data Analysis and Findings:

Gender Wise Classification:

Table 1: Gender wise Classification

S.No	Gender	No. of Respondents	%age
1	Male	33	66
2	Female	17	34
	Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

For the purpose of above table Gender has been classified into two categories. The sample consists of 66% male respondents and 34% female respondents.

Age Wise Classification:

Table 2: Age wise Classification

S.No	Age	No. of Respondents	%age
1	Below 20	9	18
2	21 – 40	27	54
3	Above 40	14	28
	Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

Table clearly shows that 54% of the respondents are in the age group of 21 – 40 years, 28% falls under the age group of above 40 and 18% of the respondents are in the age group of below 20 years.

In order to find out whether there is any significant relationship between age and satisfaction level, two way tables has been framed. Table 3 shows the age the respondents and the level of satisfaction

Table 3: Age and Level of Satisfaction

S.No	Age	Level of Opinion			Total
		Low	Medium	High	
1	Below 20	2 (22%)	4 (45%)	3 (33%)	9
2	21 – 40	5 (19%)	15(56%)	7 (25%)	27
3	Above 40	1 (7%)	9 (64%)	4 (29%)	14
	Total	8 (16%)	28 (56%)	14 (28%)	50

Source: Primary Data.

It was clear from the Table 3 that out of 50 respondents of 27 respondents are in the age group of 21-40 have medium level of satisfaction.

Hypothesis Testing:

The age-wise classification and the satisfaction level of the respondents are tested by framing following Hypothesis.

Null Hypothesis (H0):

There is no significant relationship between age and satisfaction level. Chi-square test has been applied to the hypothesis.

Degrees of Freedom = (c-1) (r-1) = (3-1) (3-1) = 4

Calculated value of χ^2 = 0.774

Table value of χ^2 0.05 = 9.49

Since, the calculate value 0.0774 is less than the table value 9.491. So hypothesis is accepted. Chi-square test proves there is no significant relationship between the gender of the respondents and the level of satisfaction.

Income Wise Classification:

Table 4: Income wise Classification

S.No	Income	No. of Respondents	%age
1	Below 5000	19	38
2	5001 – 10000	22	44

3	10001 - 15000	7	14
4	Above 15000	2	4
	Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

Table clearly shows that 44% of the respondents are in the income group of 5001 –10000, 38% falls under the income group of Below 5000 and 4% of the respondents are in the income group of above 15000.

Degree of Job Preference:

Table 5: Degree of Job preference

S.No	Degree	No. of Respondents	%age
1	Very Satisfied	9	18
2	Satisfied	27	54
3	Undecided	14	28
4	Less Satisfied	0	0
5	Dis Satisfied	0	0
	Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

The table 5 shows that out of 27 workers ,54 percent workers are satisfied with their job and only 18 percent workers are very satisfied with their job and the rest 28% of the workers are in indecision about their satisfaction level.

Co-Workers Cooperation:

Table 6: Co-workers cooperation

S.No	Degree	No. of Respondents	%age
1	Very Satisfied	30	60
2	Satisfied	7	15
3	Undecided	13	25
4	Less Satisfied	0	0
5	Dis Satisfied	0	0
	Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the table no.6, it is inferred that out of total 20 workers, 15 percent workers are satisfied with their co-workers cooperation and only 60 percent workers are very satisfied with their co-workers cooperation and other rest 25 percent workers are in indecision about their satisfaction level.

Working Environment:

Table 7: Working Environment

S.No	Degree	No. of Respondents	%age
1	Very Satisfied	15	30
2	Satisfied	25	50
3	Undecided	10	20
4	Less Satisfied	0	0
5	Dis Satisfied	0	0
	Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

Working Environment is the major factor for the level of job satisfaction. As far as satisfaction level of the respondents, 30 percent workers are just satisfied with their working environment and 50 percent employees are very satisfied with their working environment and rest 20 percent workers are in indecision about their satisfaction level.

Welfare Facilities:

Table 8: Welfare facilities

S.No	Degree	No. of Respondents	%age
1	Very Satisfied	16	32
2	Satisfied	16	32
3	Undecided	10	20
4	Less Satisfied	5	10
5	Dis Satisfied	3	6
	Total	50	100

Source: Primary Data

From the above table, researcher finds out the various satisfaction level of the workers to which they belong. It inferred that 32 percent of the respondents are very satisfied and satisfied with their welfare facilities,

10 percent workers are less satisfied with their welfare facilities, 6 percent workers are dissatisfied with their welfare facilities and rest of the 20 percent workers are in indecision about their satisfaction level.

Conclusion:

Every organization depends on their manpower for success and development. In-fact, if workers work properly, the organization can easily achieve the target. While studying the job satisfaction level of spinning mill workers, the finding is that on average they were satisfied with their jobs. Although some weaknesses exist in contents of co-worker cooperation, work environment and Welfare facilities. The result of the study indicates that layoff threats, quick turnover, less welfare schemes, and less scope for vertical growth increase job dissatisfaction. On the other hand, secure job environment, welfare policies, and job stability increase the degree of job satisfaction.

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